

Optimal Placement of Phasor Measurement Unit for Complete Observability of the Power System

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Abstract - Measurements produced by Remote Terminal Units are the main source of data used in India for power system monitoring (RTU). Because of its many capabilities, synchronized Phasor, also known as a Phasor Measurement Unit (PMU), is a common option for power system measurement in other countries and is becoming more and more popular there. PMU allows one to directly detect voltage or current phasors, which was previously impossible. Data that has been time-synchronized is provided by GPS. Installing PMU at each bus, though, is neither cost-effective nor necessary for a power system. It is necessary to establish an effective and practical PMU placement strategy with a restricted supply of PMU in order to avoid this circumstance. This article surveys and compares various PMU placement techniques for the IEEE 6 bus system using MATLAB-PSAT (Power System Analysis Toolbox). We also give a classification based on the kind of obtained observability.

Keywords: Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs), PSAT (Power System Analysis Toolbox), Optimal Placement of PMUs (OPP), Linear Static State Estimation, Power System Analysis.

1.0 Introduction

A synchrophasor, commonly referred to as a PMU (Phasor Measurement Unit), is an essential tool used in electric systems to improve operators' awareness of what is happening throughout the large grid network. A PMU is a device used to measure something known as a phasor. The magnitude and phase angle of the AC voltage or current at a particular location on a power line are represented by a phasor. This data can be utilized to establish periodicity as well as for identifying and analyzing system conditions.

This work introduces the Power System Analysis Tool (PSAT), a new MATLAB-based tool that is freely available online. PSAT comprises time-domain simulation, small-signal stability analysis, optimal power flow, continuation power flow, and power flow. A full graphical user interface and a one-line network editor built on Simulink are also included with the toolbox. The fact that the MATLAB environment is a for-profit, "closed" software that forbids both modification and free distribution is a significant but sometimes overlooked concern. Both the toolkit and the platform on which it runs should be free to enable idea exchange and significantly advance scientific research. PSAT can be used for this purpose on GNU/Octave, a free MATLAB clone.

PMUs (Phasor Measurement Units), which can be used for various monitoring, control, and

protection purposes, are utilized to monitor accurate voltage, current and frequency phasor measurements. Real-time measurements of voltage, current, phase angle, and frequency are made by the PMU which are GPS-time stamped. Data measured by the Phasor Measurement Units are sent to the Phasor Data Concentrator (PDC), which analyses, sorts, and aggregates the data for better decision-making.

2.0 Literature review

The main objective of an OPP (Optimal Placement of PMUs) problem is to reduce the total number of PMUs that must be deployed for full system traceability during maintenance. The complete electrical system can remain an observed with the help of optimal PMUs. An ideal PMU placement methodology using MATLAB's linear integer programming method is described by Sandhya Rani et al. in [1]. In the PSAT, Kaur et al. [2] discuss different PMU placement strategies. Singh et al. introduced phasor measurement in the publication. The PMU device is a crucial electrical system monitoring and control tool [3].

The model provides synchronised, real-time measurements of the bus voltage and the current phase values corresponding to the bus bars where these PMUs are installed. A topological method that uses linear binary integer programming to identify the optimal placement of PMUs for the system to be fully feasible is also introduced. The above-recommended preparation is evaluated using several IEEE test systems (buses), and the results are also developed in this article to ensure complete system monitoring both in normal mode and after the loss of one PMU.

3.0 PSAT Model of an IEEE 6 Bus System

PSAT is a MATLAB toolkit for electrical system analysis and lead operations. PSAT includes energy flow, continuous power flow, optimal power flow, time domain small signal stability simulation, and analysis. The Simulink-based library offers a user-friendly network planning tool, and all functions may be examined via graphical user interfaces. The PSAT Model of the IEEE 6 Bus System is displayed in Fig. 1.

Fig 1. PSAT Model of the IEEE 6 Bus System

4.0 Observability in Power System and Optimal Placement of PMUs (OPP)

Given a set of redundant measurements, the observability of the state of a power system is a relevant point because state estimation precedes it and requires an accurate estimate of the state to achieve secure operation. This issue is dealt with in this study using a novel strategy: the resolution of a well-behaved integer linear programming issue. Using the design of experiments and analysis of variance procedures, the generated results are statistically examined and contrasted with a conventional approach.

The method of decreasing the number of PMUs required while ensuring that the entire power system is entirely visible known as optimal phasor measurement units (PMUs) placement. When the voltages of every bus in the power system are known, the power system is considered observable.

Full Observability describes the PMU placement situation in which there are adequate PMU locations to determine all the bus voltages in a power system. The goal of PMU placement optimization is to maximize complete observability while minimizing the number of PMUs (n_p) and ideal position $S(n_p)$ of the PMUs. You can state the OPP as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min n_p \{ \max R(n_p, S(n_p)) \} \\ & \text{Such that } \text{Obs}(n_p, S(n_p)) = 1 \end{aligned}$$

Where Obs is the observability evaluation logical function and $R(n_p, S(n_p))$ is the redundancy measurement index.

A common OPP problem's principal objective is to reduce the number of PMUs that must be installed while keeping the entire system observable.

5.0 Result and Discussion

5.1 Power Flow result of the IEEE 6 bus system with PMUs

Table I shows the Power Flow result of the IEEE 6 bus system with PMUs whereas Table II represents total power generation, total load, total losses of the IEEE 6 bus system with PMUs.

TABLE I: Power flow result of the IEEE 6 bus system with PMUs

Bus	V	Phase	P gen	Q gen	P load	Q load
	[kV]	[deg]	[MW]	[MVar]	[MW]	[MVar]
Bus2	416.4	-10.8913	12	153.1984	80	60
Bus3	407.6	-6.37007	32	-16.4513	0	0
Bus4	428.4	-14.3839	24	87.0084	0	0
Bus5	330.0513	-17.3029	0	0	80	60
Bus6	314.5366	-7.53515	0	0	77.2916	57.9687
bus 1	400	0	205.3663	36.30714	0	0

TABLE II: Total power generation, total load, total losses of the IEEE 6 bus system with PMUs

Total Generation	
Real Power [MW]	273.3663
Reactive Power [MVAR]	260.0627
Total Load	
Real Power [MW]	237.2916
Reactive Power [MVAR]	177.9687
Total Losses	
Real Power [MW]	36.07468
Reactive Power [MVAR]	82.09396

5.2 Voltage, Active Power, Reactive Power Profile of the Power System with Optimally Placed PMUs

Fig. 3, Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 Voltage, Active Power, Reactive Power Profile of the Power System with Optimally Placed PMUs respectively.

Fig 3. Voltage Profile of the Power System with Optimally Placed PMUs

Fig 4. Real Power Profile of Power System with Optimally Placed PMUs

Fig 5. Reactive Profile of the Power System with Optimally Placed PMUs

5.3 PMU Placement Methodology

The Rec. (N-1) spanning Tree algorithm, Simulated Annealing, Graph Theory, and Depth First are some of the techniques for placing PMUs in their optimal positions. The optimal PMU location reduces the number of PMUs required, lowering costs and enhancing power network operation and monitoring.

Fig 6. Report on linear static state estimation using the annealing approach

Table III shows the comparison between various PMU placement techniques.

TABLE III: Comparison of various PMU Placement Techniques

Sl No.	Method to Find PMU Location	No. of PMU	Location of PMUs	No of Non-Observable Bus
1	Depth first	3	3,5,1	0
2	Graph theory	3	3,5,1	0
3	Annealing method	2	3,6	0
4	Rec. Spanning tree	2	3,6	2
5	Dir. Spanning tree	2	3,6	2
6	Rec. (N-1) Spanning tree	3	2,4,6	0

From the above table it is observed that using Annealing Method, the no. of PMU requirement is minimum and there will be no non-observable buses. Hence, we are considering Annealing Method for optimal placement of PMUs. Hence, we can reduce the cost of the system.

Conclusion

The PMU and their applications have transformed the wide area monitoring system. To the conception of the smart grid, optimal PMU placement is one step. Considering that PMUs are still expensive, it is not practical to install them in every bus in a system. At this point, the system is fully observable, it is crucial to choose the fewest possible PMUs and their placements. The number of PMUs is reduced through optimal PMU placement, which lowers expenses. The reliability of the power system is increased by the use of PMUs. Therefore, it is possible to fully monitor the system by using fewer PMUs than the system's entire number of buses.

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